

**LEARNING NEEDS ASSESSMENT OF THE SANGGUNIANG KABATAAN
OFFICIALS IN THE PROVINCE OF DAVAO DEL NORTE**

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**In Partial Fulfillment of the Requirements for the
Degree Bachelor of Public Administration**

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ABSTRACT

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The Sangguniang Kabataan (SK), established by RA 7160, is vital for youth representation and nation-building in the Philippines. However, the Sanggunian Kabataan (SK) has struggled with ineffectiveness, limited governance understanding, and inadequate training, signaling a gap between officials' competencies and their roles. This study conducts a Learning Needs Assessment for SK officials in Davao del Norte, across the three cities and eight municipalities, with a total of 223 respondents. Grounded in Human Capital Theory and Competency-Based Training (CBT), the research assesses SK officials' current core, technical, leadership, and functional competencies, along with core skills, considering their educational attainment. Using a descriptive survey with a quantitative approach, data from elected and appointed SK officials will identify specific skill and competency deficiencies. The findings informed a comprehensive training plan to boost SK officials' efficiency and effectiveness. This study offers significant contributions by pinpointing training needs, providing a foundation for policy recommendations to strengthen the SK, and guiding future research on youth leadership development in the Philippines.

Keywords: *Learning Needs Assessment, Skills and Competencies, Training and Development, Policy Recommendations, Educational Attainment, Descriptive survey, Davao del Norte, Philippines*

SDG: Goal 16 - Peace, Justice and Strong Institutions

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INTRODUCTION

The youth make up the largest, liveliest, and most active segment of society; they are essential components in any country. A nation's future becomes unstable when its young people are neglected, and the repercussions are typically severe and extensive (Castillo, Cruz, Lapaz, Marcha, Padillo, Vegiga, & Vallespin, 2024). The 1987 Philippine Constitution's Article II, Section 13 indicates that the State is dedicated to promoting and upholding the physical, moral, spiritual, intellectual, and social welfare of the youth because it recognizes their critical role in the development of the country. It will encourage young people to participate in public and civic affairs and instill in them a sense of patriotism and nationalism.

According to RA 10742, also known as the SK Reform Act, the Sangguniang Kabataan (SK) is a body established under RA 7160, also known as the Local Government Code of 1991. It was institutionalized to represent the youth of each barangay. Moreover, as cited in Balanon, Ong, Torre, and Trinidad (2017), the specific roles of Sangguniang Kabataan include the initiation of programs to carry out objectives, promulgation of resolutions and policies, consultations with local youth organizations for formulating policy and implementation of programs, and tapping the appropriate agency to implement programs and projects.

Furthermore, following the SK Reform Act of 2015, Sangguniang Kabataan officials, whether elected or appointed, shall undergo mandatory and continuing training programs before he or she can assume office. They are required to participate in the ongoing training initiatives that the Commission will carry out in collaboration with the DILG. Deliberate non-attendance at the aforementioned training sessions will be sufficient to disqualify the LYDC member or Sangguniang Kabataan official in question, or subject them to disciplinary action. To help Sangguniang Kabataan officials better understand and utilize the authority and responsibilities granted to them by the Sangguniang Kabataan Reform Act of 2015, the Department of the Interior and Local Government (DILG) should continue to host

leadership events, training sessions, seminars, and information drives (Erlina, Boncalo, Gortifacion, Sumampong, Montalba, Ganto, & Chua, 2023).

However, Erlina, Boncalo, Gortifacion, Sumampong, Montalba, Ganto, and Chua (2023) stated that Sangguniang Kabataan, under its current structure, had lost its effectiveness in advancing the democratic ideals in service-oriented youth. This governing body seemed to be losing the trust of the public. This could be because they lacked sufficient knowledge of good governance, received inadequate training, were involved in graft and corruption, or lacked sufficient experience in public service, which makes it harder for them to perform their job of serving the community. According to Ivanyna and Salerno (2021), a government's ability to promote equitable growth can be significantly hindered by poor governance. The competence view of corruption overlooks the systemic impact on development, arguing that it may "grease the wheels" of the economy.

In addition, concerns of theft and nepotism have also affected public trust, leading to the belief that the SK occasionally prioritizes its own interests before public services. To develop targeted solutions, it is significant to look into the underlying reasons for corruption in the SK (Guelos, Duncara, Helbolario, & Villarosa, 2024). Moreover, the absence of continuous development programs, training, and learning leads to ineffective quality service. Without a structured process that will address these challenges, the ability of SK officials will continue to be a concern in the field of local governance.

Training Needs Analysis (TNA) was first introduced in the book called "Training in Business and Industry" by McGehee and Thayer in 1961. Since then, many organizations have used training needs analysis as a basis to bridge the gap between actual training needs and individual knowledge and skills. Although there are other methods for performing TNA, McGhee and Thayer's Three Level Analysis is one that is frequently used (Fatima, 2024). According to Sundari and Aksara (2022), in essence, training needs analysis is a data collection technique used to compare and identify the organization's actual performance level with the expected or planned performance level. Training is required when a person's competencies and

what they must do to perform their job effectively are not aligned. One way to ascertain whether there is a training need and, if so, what training is required to close the gap is through a training needs analysis.

Similarly, according to Markaki, Malhotra, Billings, and Theus (2021). TNA explains the current level of an individual's efficiency, the skill areas that require the most improvement, and the best approaches to accomplish them. It is an essential step in creating training plans, the instrument that guides the development of tailored training to address the needs of professional growth. Training is a fundamental instrument in developing a work efficiency culture; hence, an organization must provide development programs and construct training that addresses the efficiency gap of its workers (Ibrahim, Boerhannoeddin & Bakare, 2017). Identifying the population's learning needs through a systematic consultation is the first step in developing an acceptable and successful training cycle. Following this should be the planning, execution, evaluation, and assurance of training transfer. Because of this, TNA's involvement is essential to making sure the training program covers the gaps in the knowledge and skills that employees need to achieve the organization's objectives and prevent resource waste (Kodwani, 2017). In this study, TNA helped determine the skills and competency gaps among SK officials, allowing the study to identify the training needs they needed to close the gaps.

Competency-based training (CBT) originated in the mid-1960s as a popular method in Australia for vocational education and training (VET) (Sandhu, 2023). For the past 30 years, it has served as the primary training paradigm in the VET sector when state education departments were concerned about inadequate teacher training programs and low student achievement (McKenna, 1992). CBT is centered on clear, measurable objectives that relate directly to instructional activities. Trainees do posttest performance assessments to see if they have mastered the necessary attitudes, skills, and information. Instructors or supervisors review these results, make any program changes, and provide additional training and mentoring to trainees who did not understand the content. Similarly, this theory corresponds with the objectives of the study, which are to assess the level of skills and competency of

the Sangguniang Kabataan (SK) officials and develop a training plan based on their results.

American economists Theodore Shultz and Gary Becker created the Human Capital Theory in 1950. Human capital theory holds that education is like an investment that pays off in the future (Leoni, 2025). Furthermore, the theory suggests that greater education and skill development can help human beings become more productive. By increasing their level of education or acquiring new skills, an individual can enhance their human capital (Ross, 2024). This theory supports the assessment of SK officials' competencies and the significance of their level of education in determining how successful they are in their roles. It may strengthen the need for training programs intended to improve their skills.

The purpose of this study is to assess the learning needs of Sangguniang Kabataan (SK) officials in three (3) cities and eight (8) municipalities in the province of Davao del Norte. This involves identifying the gender and local demographics of Sangguniang Kabataan (SK) officials, as well as their training preferences in project development, volunteer mobilization, and common skills. Additionally, the study will assess their proficiency in technical, functional, leadership, and core skills. Furthermore, it will evaluate their competence across core, leadership, technical, and functional abilities. Moreover, the study's results provide a valuable basis for policy recommendations on how to improve the core of Sangguniang Kabataan (SK), ensuring that training and development conducted address the overall specific needs of SK officials to perform their duties efficiently and effectively.

Figure 1 demonstrates the conceptual framework of the study, the primary objective of which is to get the demographic profile of the Sangguniang Kabataan (SK) officials within the scope of Davao del Norte and their perceived trainings, assess the current level of skills and competencies of Sangguniang Kabataan (SK) officials in terms of core competencies, technical competencies, leadership competencies, functional expertise, and core skills through the use of survey

questionnaires and statistical analysis, and develop a training plan intended for Sangguniang Kabataan.

Figure 1. Conceptual Framework of the Study

Using a survey questionnaire, the data were collected from the Sangguniang Kabataan (SK) officials from the different cities and municipalities in Davao del Norte. The analyzed data helped identify the most important training and served as the basis for developing a new training plan—a training plan that is composed of mandatory training and is arranged from the most needed training at the top to the least needed training.

The significance of the study lies in its potential to give the government valuable information that allows them to come up with better ways to make the Sangguniang Kabataan (SK) officials in Davao del Norte province more efficient and effective. Additionally, the Department of Interior and Local Government (DILG) can use this survey to find out what problems the Sangguniang Kabataan in the

Philippines are experiencing. Pimentel (2007) points out that the DILG is very important for giving power to local communities by helping them grow their capacity, formulate policies, and directly make this study relevant to their strategic objectives.

It is also important to the Sangguniang Kabataan (SK) officials in particular since it provides them with valuable information which they can use to enhance themselves as leaders in order to achieve a better and more prepared youth government. Besides its short-term practical applications, the study also provides a solid foundation for future scholarly studies of the importance of training needs assessments and effective youth leadership. The study contributed to future research studies since it indicated critical areas to be investigated and areas of gaps in the body of knowledge on this topic. Creswell and Creswell (2018) stress that this iterative research process, in which each study builds upon its predecessors, is crucial for promoting academic understanding and supporting evidence-based policymaking.

Despite efforts to address the pressing issues facing the Sangguniang Kabataan, there is a notable gap in the existing literature regarding the continuous training of the Sangguniang Kabataan. At the same time, numerous studies have delved into identifying the effectiveness of mandatory trainings and seminars, like the study of Cal, Abellanosa, Payao and Niere (2023), wherein they concluded that the Sangguniang Kabataan Mandatory Training implemented in the chosen barangays in Cebu is effective and has shown a favorable correlation between knowledge and the conduct of training for SK. Few have examined what training and programs are most needed to address the skills and competency gap that resulted in the issues of the Sangguniang Kabataan. Moreover, a study conducted by Carolino and Rouco (2022) revealed that structured training programs significantly enhance leadership skills in young leaders, highlighting the importance of strategic and continuous development training that best supports their leadership skills. In contrast, the lack of cooperation from Sangguniang Kabataan (SK) officials can hinder development and competence, resulting in unequal distribution of respondents.

The scope of the study surrounds all barangays in the Province of Davao del Norte, and the respondents are elected and appointed Sangguniang Kabataan (SK) officials. This comprehensive coverage ensures that the research captures a wide and representative sample of SK officials across the province, allowing for a thorough examination of their competencies, training needs, and developmental requirements. Similarly, a study by Palangdao, Dumpayan, Perez, Aquino, and Ramos, (2023) concluded that Sangguniang Kabataan (SK) officials in Negros Occidental demonstrated a strong combination of core, technical, and leadership competencies, particularly in community engagement, effective communication, and project management. However, there are notable gaps that were observed and remained prevalent, especially in financial management, budgeting, and strategic planning, which are critical for sustaining successful community participation. Especial, Melitante, and Janer, (2022) highlighted persistent communication gaps among the Sangguniang Kabataan (SK) officials, recommending a structured training plan that fosters collaboration and effective communication.

Furthermore, Castillo et al. (2024), as cited in the study of Suarez and Tuble (2025), emphasize the need for communication pathways between Sangguniang Kabataan (SK) officials and their constituents to enhance governance outcomes. In addition, it is imperative to proceed with a descriptive survey design to assess the level of competency of the Sangguniang Kabataan (SK) officials and to identify strengths. It's important to note that this study focuses specifically on the elected and appointed SK officials. It explicitly excludes other barangay officials, such as barangay chairpersons and councilors, to keep the focus clear and sharp on youth leadership. In conclusion, the results and recommendations directly spoke to the unique roles and responsibilities of the SK officials, without mixing their skills and challenges with those of other local government leaders. This way, the study stayed true to understanding and supporting the youth sector. Within the framework of quantitative research, the study employed a descriptive research design. As a result, the conclusions were based on the descriptive analysis.

METHOD

Study Respondents

The study focused on the elected and appointed Sangguniang Kabataan (SK) officials across the two districts of Davao del Norte. The province of Davao del Norte is composed of eleven (11) Local Government Units (LGUs) with three (3) cities and eight (8) municipalities and a total of 220 barangays. Following this, the respondents were selected using a simple random sampling method. This is based on the concept of Graglia (2025), which suggests that a rule of thumb or ten percent (10%) of the total respondent population is sufficient for survey sample sizes. Since the total number of SK officials is 2230, the examination of this 10 percent rule of thumb provided an adequate sample size of 223 respondents. In addition, this value is also consistent with the statement of Memon, Ting, Cheah, Thurasamy, Chuah, and Cham (2020) that a sample size of 200 is relatively adequate to conduct research. Moreover, 223 respondents participated in this study, 111 respondents (49.8%) identified as female, while 112 respondents (50.2%) identified as male. This strategy and approach ensured that all Sangguniang Kabataan officials from different municipalities in the province were fully represented. All of the chosen participants had already taken an initial survey. Using random sampling and the rule-of-thumb method makes it possible to identify any disparities in experiences between the several groups that took part in the study.

Materials and Instruments

In this study, a survey questionnaire was adapted from the National Youth Commission's (2021) Guidebook on the Competency Framework for SKs and LYDOs and PAGPAKANUG (2024). The purpose of the study was to identify the training requirements of the Sangguniang Kabataan through obtaining their demographics, desire for training, the level of skills and competence attributed to the respondents, and educational attainment as a mitigating factor.

The survey questionnaire assessed the training needs by focusing on the variables and their indicators. Primarily, the demographic profile includes the gender and locality of the respondents. It is followed by the skills and competencies with the indicators of core competencies, technical competencies, leadership competencies, and functional competencies. Lastly, the specific training and development were composed of common skills, project development, and volunteer mobilization.

The researchers evaluated the reliability and validity of the questions by executing a pilot test with 37 respondents. Using Cronbach's alpha, the reliability test results showed that all scales in the questionnaire demonstrated high to very high consistency, with Cronbach's alpha values exceeding the acceptable threshold of 0.700. All scales in the questionnaire demonstrated a strong internal consistency. This aligns with Hussey, Alsalti, Bosco, Elson, and Arslan (2025), who note that alpha values above 0.70 reflect acceptable reliability. The questions were validated by the professor and were distributed to the Sangguniang Kabataan (SK) officials in three (3) cities and eight (8) municipalities of Davao del Norte province. After the questionnaire was answered by the respondents, the data were tallied, tabulated, and assessed according to how often the respondents marked an item. In analyzing, the researchers engaged a statistician to help identify adequate statistical methods to be used in analyzing the acquired data from the respondents. Quantitatively, it revealed the training needs of the Sangguniang Kabataan (SK) officials.

Table 1 shows the competency matrix, which outlines four key areas: core competencies, technical competencies, leadership competencies, and functional expertise. Each area details specific competencies, such as adaptability and information management, along with behavioral indicators that describe how these competencies are demonstrated. The matrix also establishes the proficiency levels and identifies a point in the focus of training needs analysis on each area of competencies, whereby it will assess and advance the skills of the Sangguniang Kabataan (SK) officials in such areas as strategic thinking, project monitoring, and financial management.

Table 1: Competency matrix

Competency area	Specific Competencies	Proficiency levels	Training needs analysis focus
Core Competencies	Adaptability Communicating Effectively Organizational Awareness	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Very High Proficiency - High Proficiency - Proficient - Low Proficiency - Very Low Proficiency 	Evaluate the competency level of SK officials and their capability to adapt to and strategize situations.
Technical competencies	Information and Management Research Aptitude Project Monitoring and Evaluation Technical Writing		Provide practical and specialized expertise to perform the core tasks of a specific job or field efficiently, in compliance with the accurate process.
Leadership competencies	Effective Decision Making Planning for Results Strategic Thinking		To develop a sense of effective leadership in terms of planning and strategic thinking.
Functional expertise	Financial Management and Budgeting Training Management		The goal is to identify the gaps in the skills and knowledge that are needed to perform specific functions and responsibilities efficiently.

Design and Procedure

The study used a Quantitative descriptive design. Quantitative approach, by Creswell (2014), is a type of research study that is quantitative descriptive, where structured forms of collecting information, such as survey questionnaires, are used to

gather information because the data collected is considered to be reliable and objective. After the data was gathered, the statistical tools were applied. The descriptive statistics played an important role in developing a clear image of their demographics and defining their needs in terms of specific training, which offers a guideline for further research.

Figure 2. Descriptive Quantitative Method Model Source: Creswell (2014)

Figure 2 demonstrates the model used, which was appropriate for the study in which the researchers assessed the respondents' level of skills and competencies and educational background as a moderating variable in order to ascertain the Sanguniang Kabataan's training needs. In order to establish the profile of the respondents and collect the data needed for the study, the researchers employed a survey questionnaire.

The respondents were contacted by sending a letter requesting permission to administer the survey as part of the quantitative phase of the study. The letter was issued in order to inform them about the necessity to participate in the research and to determine the time and day suitable for the respondent. After the respondents gave their permission, the survey questionnaire was sent through Google Forms to the Sangguniang Kabataan officials. The survey questionnaire was based on a Likert scale that was used to evaluate the respondents' agreement or disagreement with each topic.

In this study, an analysis of quantitative data will be conducted with the aim of involving the data in quantitative methodologies, which means processed data. The means, standard deviations, and the range of scores were used to characterize the results with the help of the descriptive statistics of the variable scores. Analysis and collation of data will be done thoroughly after administering the structured survey questionnaire.

The validation, reliability, and unbiased collection of data are important in quantitative research in order to achieve a desirable and equally credible result. Validity means that the instruments or measures used will reflect what we aim to analyze, as well as provide the actual real situation. It is normally achieved through the application of tested and established tools. Reliability, conversely, means the level of stability and consistency of these measurements over time. The use of reliable data increases the credibility of the outcomes and enables their implementation in every case (Surucu & Maslakci, 2020). The factors listed above affect the reliability and accuracy of quantitative research and assist in gaining confidence in the findings of the research (Abbas, 2023).

Ethics is necessary in quantitative research to ensure that the research is ethical enough to preserve the integrity of a study and research participant safety. Researchers also observe their ethical standings by seeking the informed consent of the participants and by ensuring that they are aware of the fact that their answer will be recorded to serve as the foundation of the study. There is a focus on voluntary participation and the individual decisions made by the respondents to say no are respected. Concurrently, the provision of precise and pertinent information pertaining to the study questions was required by ethical behavior. Privacy protection is another important consideration, and confidentiality is strictly upheld after data collection by using pseudonyms in accordance with the Data Privacy Act of 2012 (R.A. 10173).

As researchers, ethical principles are significant, which deal with informed consent, confidentiality, putting the welfare of the participant first, and adopting ethical principles, which concern informed consent, confidentiality and putting the welfare of the participant first. Such guidelines must be continuously monitored and addressed during the course of the study. In the Republic of the Philippines, Republic Act No. 10173 or the Data Privacy Act of 2012 reinforces these ethical principles and aligns the legal requirements to its ethical research study.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Demographic Profile of Respondents

Table 2 shows the demographic profile of the 223 respondents who provided essential context for understanding the study's sample. The sample exhibited a near-even distribution across genders. Specifically, 111 respondents (49.8%) identified as female, while 112 respondents (50.2%) identified as male. This balanced representation is crucial for evaluating the representativeness of the sample in terms of sex, which is vital for assessing the generalizability of the findings.

Table 2: Frequency Distribution of Respondents by Sex

Sex	Frequency	Percent	Cumulative Percent
Female	111	49.8	49.8
Male	112	50.2	100.0
Total	223	100.0	

Educational Attainment of Respondents

Table 3 presents the educational background of the respondents, which indicates a sample largely composed of individuals with higher education. The majority of respondents answered having a "College Level" education, accounting for 158 individuals (70.9%). This was followed by "College Graduate" status, represented by 44 respondents (19.7%). A smaller proportion had a "High School" education (16 respondents, 7.2%), with "Graduate Level" (4 respondents, 1.8%) and "Vocational" (1 respondent, 0.4%) comprising the smallest segments of the sample. This demographic characteristic can significantly influence perceptions, knowledge, and engagement with various concepts, providing important context for interpreting the study's findings.

Table 3: Frequency Distribution of Respondents by Educational Attainment

Educational Attainment	Frequency	Percent	Cumulative Percent
High School	16	7.2	7.2
College Level	158	70.9	78.0
College Graduate	44	19.7	97.8
Graduate Level	4	1.8	99.6
Vocational	1	.4	100.0
Total	223	100.0	

Distribution of Instrument (City/Municipality)

Table 4 presents the respondents' range of cities and municipalities that participated in the data collection. Kapalong was the most represented area with 52 respondents (23.3%), followed by Tagum with 41 respondents (18.4%), and New Corella with 34 respondents (15.2%). Carmen (30 respondents, 13.5%) and Panabo (25 respondents, 11.2%) also contributed substantially to the sample, while other areas such as Asuncion, Samal, and Talaingod had minimal representation.

Although the Island Garden City of Samal (IGACOS) has one of the biggest populations in the province of Davao del Norte, it has the fewest respondents due to a lack of cooperation from the SK Federation and its officials. Lastimado et al. (2025) stressed that the lack of cooperation from Local Government Units (LGUs) often forces Sangguniang Kabataan (SK) officials to scale down or cancel projects; several factors influence this, such as unclear communication and bureaucratic bottlenecks, reducing the efficiency of Sangguniang Kabataan. Moreover, Maurel, Ayop, Juriana, and Lagura, (2025) stressed that some perceptions and decisions of youth are still influenced by people around them. This makes it a challenge and creates gaps for researchers who are delving into this field of study.

Table 4. Frequency Distribution of Respondents by City/Municipality

Local Government Unit (LGU)	Frequency	Percent
Asuncion	4	1.8
Carmen	30	13.5
Kapalong	52	23.3
NewCorella	34	15.2
Panabo	25	11.2
Samal	1	.4
SanIsidro	21	9.4
StoTomas	14	6.3
Tagum	41	18.4
Talaingod	1	.4
Total	223	100.0

Self-assessed Skills and Competency Assessment Level (SaCSCALE)

Core Competency

Table 5 shows the individual core competency items under the variable of Self-assessed Skills and Competency Assessment Level (SaCSCALE) of SK officials, which had mean scores ranging from 2.1973 to 2.4664. All individual items, like the total Core Competencies score ($M=2.2996$), fell under the "low proficiency" category. This precise information enables a more detailed knowledge of which components of core competencies are evaluated negatively. The lowest mean score for core competency, namely "decision making," followed by the "organizational awareness" component, got a score of ($M=1.2691$). This data highlights a need to address the specific issues hampering the ability of Sangguniang Kabataan (SK) officials to serve their community. Lising and Rivera (2024) support the idea that core

competencies, especially organizational awareness, need enhancement because SK officials can benefit from improved organizational awareness to navigate local government structures more effectively.

Table 5. Mean Scores of Core Competency

Core Competency	N	Mean	Descriptive Analysis
Adaptability	223	2.4664	Low proficiency
Communicating Effectively	223	2.2960	Low proficiency
Organizational Awareness	223	2.2691	Low proficiency
Commitment to Serve the Filipino Youth	223	2.691	Low proficiency
Decision Making	223	2.1973	Low Proficiency
Overall Mean	223	2.2996	Low proficiency

Legend:

1:00 – 1:80 Very low proficiency

2:61 – 3:40 Proficient

4:21 – 5:00 Very high proficiency

1:81 – 2:60 Low proficiency

3:41 – 4:20 High proficiency

Technical Competency

Table 6 presents average scores for the components of technical competency, which range between 2.2691 and 2.3948. Every individual item reached the “Low Proficiency” level, confirming the overall technical competency mean of $M=2.3058$. “Problem Analysis and Resolution” recorded the lowest mean at 2.2691, followed closely by “Technical Writing” at 2.2915. Both scores remain firmly within the range of “Low Proficiency,” and this granular data highlights particular technical skills that may be deficient or causing concern within the surveyed group. This finding is in line with the research conducted to investigate SK project implementation in Davao City, which found that low technical competency is a major issue that deters the performance of the youth councils. Issues like insufficient support system, absence of systematized training courses, diminished autonomy, and ineffective communication were revealed by SK officials to impede successful project implementation (Austria, Bonilla, Cabiles, & Rupinta, 2024). The paper suggests that strategic training should be conducted in planning and project management, as well as training SK officials in

enhancing their technical expertise and overall contribution.

Table 6. Mean Scores of Technical Competency

Technical Competency	N	Mean	Descriptive Analysis
Information Management	223	2.3498	Low proficiency
Problem Analysis and Resolution	223	2.2691	Low proficiency
Understanding of Youth Development	223	2.3004	Low proficiency
Project Execution	223	2.3184	Low proficiency
Technical Writing	223	2.2915	Low Proficiency
Overall Mean	223	2.3058	Low proficiency

Legend:

1:00 – 1:80 Very low proficiency
1:81 – 2:60 Low proficiency

2:61 – 3:40 Proficient
3:41 – 4:20 High proficiency

4:21 – 5:00 Very high proficiency

Leadership Competency

Table 7 shows the mean scores for the components of leadership competency; items showed scores ranging from 2.2332 to 2.2870. The overall mean of leadership competency is 2.2709, falling under the category of "Low Proficiency" level. Moreover, the lowest item, which is "Building Partnerships and Alliances for Youth Advocacy," scored a mean of 2.2332, indicating a "Low Proficiency" level in this category.

This table provides specific insights into perceived weaknesses in leadership attributes or practices among the respondents; hence, it is imperative to address these issues accordingly. A study conducted by Suarez and Tuble (2025) emphasizes that fostering culture and open dialogue can help bridge these perceived gaps. Strengthening these competencies is essential for Sangguniang Kabataan (SK) officials to fulfill their mandate as catalysts of youth development and community transformation. This can ensure that SK governance is aligned with community expectations and grounded in collaborative leadership practices.

Table 7. Mean Scores of Leadership Competency

Leadership Competency	N	Mean	Descriptive Analysis
Building Partnerships and Alliances for Youth Advocacy	223	2.2332	Low proficiency
Effective Decision Making	223	2.2780	Low proficiency
Fostering Collaboration and Consensus for the Youth	223	2.2870	Low proficiency
Strategic Thinking	223	2.2780	Low proficiency
Embracing Change	223	2.2780	Low Proficiency
Overall Mean	223	2.2709	Low proficiency

Legend:

1:00 – 1:80 Very low proficiency

2:61 – 3:40 Proficient

4:21 – 5:00 Very high proficiency

1:81 – 2:60 Low proficiency

3:41 – 4:20 High proficiency

Functional Expertise

Table 8 shows the mean scores of items under functional expertise, ranging from 2.2691 to the lowest mean score of 2.23901, which is "Policy Development." The overall mean score of functional expertise fell under the "Low Proficiency" level, pinpointing that Ineffective performance often stems from a lack of competencies and functional performance that are perceived as low by the respondents (Lising & Rivera, 2024). Thus, acquiring the necessary functional expertise can help you grasp ideas on how to resolve challenges or help you make reasonable decisions in your workplace (Indeed Career Advice, 2025).

Consequently, the findings highlight that without a quick intervention in improving the Sangguniang Kabataan (SK) officials in these critical areas, the organization risks stagnation, as functional competence is one of the foundations upon which strategic execution is built.

Table 8 . Mean Scores of Functional Expertise

Functional Expertise	N	Mean	Descriptive Analysis
Financial Management and Budgeting	223	2.3543	Low proficiency
Training Management	223	2.3094	Low proficiency
Policy Development	223	2.3901	Low proficiency
Human Resource Management and Development	223	2.3004	Low proficiency
General Services Management	223	2.2691	Low Proficiency
Overall Mean	223	2.3247	Low proficiency

Legend:

1:00 – 1:80 Very low proficiency

2:61 – 3:40 Proficient

4:21 – 5:00 Very high proficiency

1:81 – 2:60 Low proficiency

3:41 – 4:20 High proficiency

This empirical data indicates that the Sangguniang Kabataan (SK) officials in the province of Davao del Norte exhibit low proficiency across all measured competencies, with mean scores ranging from 2.2709 to 2.3274 across various indicators. These findings suggest that SK officials currently lack the necessary skills and knowledge to effectively perform their roles. According to Lising and Rivera (2024) core competencies such as adaptability, commitment to serve the youth, and effective communication, along with strong technical competencies in financial management, budgeting, problem analysis, and policy development, project monitoring, and collaboration skills, which are part of their functional expertise are essential to bridge the gap between the SK's mandate and actual performance in youth governance. Additionally, the poor performance in the leadership competency is likely to be alarming, since leadership skills are important in mobilizing participation, conflict management, and development progress within the community. Youth officials trained in leadership gain confidence in their decisions and actions,

and this leads directly to the establishment of more efficient governance (Pasicaran-Escleto, Cabatingan, Polinar, & Delantar, 2024).

The above findings are important to enhance the governance skills of SK officials and service delivery to the youth. As Manaban (2024) explains, limited knowledge and skills challenge their professional preparedness and community leadership. The proficiency in the training areas directly assimilates with the proficiency in core, technical, leadership, and functional competencies, whose proficiency is quite low. It follows that a low level of the same competencies among SK officials discourages effective participation of youths in the development of projects and mobilization of volunteers, as hallmark roles in facilitating the development of communities, which is fundamentally relevant to good governance. Consequently, this underscores the significance of a more detailed customized training in the ordinary skills, project generation, and volunteer recruitment, guaranteeing better competent and skilled SK officials in the Province of Davao del Norte.

Strategic Training and Development Evaluation Variable (STaDEV)

Common Skills

Table 9 shows the common skills items under the Strategic Training and Development Evaluation Variable (STaDEV) of SK officials, which had mean scores ranging from 2.1883 to 2.4993. In addition, all twelve items and the overall mean of common skills consistently fell under the category of "Low Proficiency." The study of Bawit et al. (2024) emphasizes the importance of enhancing youth participation in environmental programs such as Disaster Risk Reduction Management, which can cultivate a culture of ecological responsibility. Ajayi-Majebi (2020) stresses the importance of equipping youth with the knowledge and skills to address environmental challenges and promote sustainability. Furthermore, this table enables a more detailed diagnosis of specific strengths and weaknesses as perceived by the respondents.

Table 9 . Mean Scores of Common Skills

Common Skills	N	Mean	Descriptive Analysis
1. Project Development and Implementation	223	2.3363	Low proficiency
2. Disaster-Risk and Reduction Management (<i>RA 10121</i>)	223	2.3543	Low proficiency
3. Parliamentary Procedure	223	2.3722	Low proficiency
4. Policy Analysis	223	2.3004	Low proficiency
5. Social media-based Government	223	2.2870	Low Proficiency
6. Financial Management	223	2.3498	Low proficiency
8. Research and Extension Training	223	2.1883	Low proficiency
9. Graphic Design	223	2.4484	Low proficiency
10. Procurement Systems	223	2.4933	Low proficiency
11. Knowledge Management	223	2.4305	Low proficiency
12. Human Behavior in Organizations	223	2.2870	Low proficiency
Overall Mean	223	2.3247	Low proficiency

Legend:

1:00 – 1:80 Very low proficiency

2:61 – 3:40 Proficient

4:21 – 5:00 Very high proficiency

1:81 – 2:60 Low proficiency

3:41 – 4:20 High proficiency

Project Development

The items included in the component of project development are as shown in Table 10, with a mean score of 2.2601 to 2.3498. Everything related to the project development variable constantly belonged to the category of Low Proficiency, similar to the overall mean score ($M=2.3056$). This table helps specify certain problems that are perceived to be present in the project development field and which could be adopted to realize the preferred training project of the Sangguniang Kabataan (SK) officials. In relation, this fits with the notion of Training Needs Analysis (TNA), where training is required when a person's competencies and what they must do to perform

their job effectively are not linked, as the project development of SK officials achieved a low proficiency level.

Table 10. Mean Scores of Project Development

Project Development	N	Mean	Descriptive Analysis
Aligning Projects in Sustainable Development Goals	223	2.3004	Low proficiency
Project Planning Tools	223	2.2870	Low proficiency
Writing Project Proposals	223	2.2601	Low proficiency
Risk and Stakeholders Management	223	2.3498	Low proficiency
Cost Planning	223	2.3184	Low Proficiency
Agile Project Execution	223	2.2915	Low Proficiency
Project Reporting and Closure Tools	223	2.3318	Low Proficiency
Overall Mean	223	2.3056	Low proficiency

Legend:

1:00 – 1:80 Very low proficiency

2:61 – 3:40 Proficient

4:21 – 5:00 Very high proficiency

1:81 – 2:60 Low proficiency

3:41 – 4:20 High proficiency

Volunteer Mobilization

Table 11 shows the volunteer mobilization items, which yielded mean scores ranging from 2.3004 to 2.3901. The overall mean of the volunteer mobilization score (M=2.3426) falls under the "Low Proficiency" level, together with the other items. This data offers specific insights into the perceived levels of volunteerism and morale, which are crucial indicators of organizational or community health. This result agrees with the study of Cadano (2024), which states that youth have low community engagement or participation in this type of civic activity due to common reasons such as lack of interest, lack of confidence, poor communication, lack of time because of personal responsibilities like schoolwork, and financial constraints or the unavailability of resources.

Table 11. Mean Scores of Volunteer Mobilization

Volunteer Mobilization	N	Mean	Descriptive Analysis
Third Sector Partnerships	223	2.3498	Low proficiency
Strategic Planning for NGOs	223	2.3901	Low proficiency
Voluntary Sector Management	223	2.3363	Low proficiency
Global Standards for Volunteering	223	2.3363	Low proficiency
Legal Basis of Voluntary Sector Management (RA 9418)	223	2.3004	Low Proficiency
Overall Mean	223	2.3426	Low proficiency

Legend:

1:00 – 1:80 Very low proficiency

2:61 – 3:40 Proficient

4:21 – 5:00 Very high proficiency

1:81 – 2:60 Low proficiency

3:41 – 4:20 High proficiency

These findings show that Sangguniang Kabataan (SK) officials in Davao del Norte have low proficiency in all key training areas: common skills (mean = 2.3412), project development (mean = 2.3056), and volunteer mobilization (mean = 2.3426), with an overall mean of 2.3298. These scores, which fall within the "low proficiency" range, mirror the findings for the independent variables—core competency, technical, leadership competency, and functional expertise—which also registered low proficiency. This parallel outcome indicates a direct correlation; the lack of foundational competencies among SK officials is reflected in their limited abilities to perform essential training-related tasks. The deficiencies in core, technical, leadership, and functional skills are contributing to SK officials' struggles in practical areas such as project management and volunteer mobilization (Naval, Donato, Salinas, & Liwan, 2023).

The findings demonstrate that there is an urgent need to engage in full-scale and tailored training for Sangguniang Kabataan (SK) officials. Unless the core areas, including common skills, project development, and volunteer mobilization, are reinforced, SK officials might not be able to fulfill their duties in youth leadership and community development. In a study of Lato and Dela Pea (2019), it was highlighted that low proficiency in technical and functional skills of SK officials in Liloan, Cebu,

directly affects their effectiveness in practical governance activities, project development, and the mobilization of volunteers. The researchers pointed out that in order to enhance SK performance and effectiveness, these competency gaps must be addressed. Thus, the integrality of training interventions that address the needs of basic and advanced skills is very important to empower SK officials.

Proposed Training Plan

Executive Summary

Training is a fundamental instrument in developing a work efficiency culture; hence, an organization must provide development programs and construct training that addresses the efficiency gap of its workers (Ibrahim et al, 2017). According to Flores III, Mendoza, Yap, and Valencia (2021), while training has been undertaken for SK Chairs at various levels and with various modules prior to their assumption, the absence of standard modules and the deployment of the right resource persons led to varying degrees of effectiveness according to several SK informants. This finding calls for a training plan intended to address issues faced by Sangguniang Kabataan (SK) officials in the country. Moreover, the study revealed that several SK officials shared difficulties navigating through administrative and government processes without proper training and manuals. As a result, an extensive five to ten (5–10) year capacity-building and youth development program intended for Sangguniang Kabataan (SK) officials in the province of Davao del Norte is outlined in this report, along with a strategic roadmap. This approach seeks to develop SK officials into exceptionally competent, moral, and flexible youth leaders by building on the fundamental understandings gained from the Training Needs Analysis (TNA).

The main goal is also to enable these officials to regularly create and implement effective youth development programs, encourage civic engagement, and make a substantial contribution to long-term community advancement that is in line with both provincial and national development objectives. In order to ensure long-term impact and adaptability, the roadmap also highlights a multifaceted

approach that includes advanced specialization, policy integration, training institutionalization, and thorough monitoring and evaluation.

Alignment with National Youth Development Plan (PYDP) and Regional Development Plans

The strategic roadmap is firmly anchored in the Philippine Youth Development Plan (PYDP), which serves as the comprehensive national blueprint for youth welfare and empowerment, spearheaded by the National Youth Commission (NYC). Such arrangements ensure national relevance and support. It is explicitly aligned with the Davao Regional Development Plan (DRDP), ensuring that local youth initiatives led by SK contribute directly to broader regional goals of inclusive growth, peace and order, good governance, and sustainable development. Additionally, by aligning the SK capacity-building strategy with established national and regional development plans, the program gains strategic legitimacy, facilitates access to broader resources, and ensures its initiatives are not isolated but integrated into the larger, coordinated development agenda of the Philippines. Moreover, government programs are most effective and sustainable when they are embedded within existing policy and planning frameworks.

Long-Term Outcomes for Youth Governance and Community Development

Enhanced Strategic Planning and Implementation: SK officials will consistently formulate and execute high-quality, evidence-based Comprehensive Barangay Youth Development Plans (CBYDPs) and Annual Barangay Youth Investment Plans (ABYIPs) that effectively address local youth issues, demonstrating a clear understanding of their mandate and planning processes.

Fiscal Prudence and Transparency: There will be demonstrably improved financial management, adherence to procurement guidelines, and full public disclosure of SK funds, ensuring accountability and maximizing the impact of the 10% barangay budget allocation.

Stakeholder Engagement and Resource Mobilization: SK officials will proactively establish and strengthen collaborative partnerships with diverse stakeholders, including government agencies, non-governmental organizations (NGOs), and the private sector, to leverage resources, expand program reach, and foster collective action for youth initiatives.

Cultivation of Ethical and Inclusive Leadership: SK officials will consistently demonstrate ethical conduct, uphold accountability, practice gender sensitivity, and foster an inclusive environment in all youth initiatives and community engagements, reflecting a commitment to good governance.

Data-Driven Decision Making: Regular conduct of youth profiling, establishment, and maintenance of updated youth databases will inform evidence-based policy and program design, ensuring interventions are targeted and responsive to actual needs.

SK as a Talent Catalyst: SK will serve as a recognized and effective pathway for continuous professional development, attracting and nurturing aspiring youth leaders, and serving as a breeding ground for future leaders in local and national public service.

Table 14. Pillars of Sustained Youth Leadership Development

Pillar	Key Competency Focus	Key Modules/Topics
Pillar 1	Foundational Governance and Critical Thinking	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • SK Mandate & Legal Framework • Advanced Information Analysis & Data Interpretation • Critical Thinking & Problem-Solving • Effective Decision-Making
Pillar 2	Strategic Youth Project Design & Implementation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Comprehensive Youth Issue Analysis & Needs Assessment • Innovative Solution Generation & Program Design • Advanced Project Planning & Management Tools • Effective Project Proposal Drafting & Grant Writing
Pillar 3	Collaborative Leadership & Community Mobilization	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Advanced Stakeholder Mapping & Engagement Strategies • Strategic Partnership Building & Management • Effective Volunteer Mobilization & Management • Advanced Conflict Resolution & Consensus Building
Pillar 4	Operational Excellence & Fiscal Responsibility	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Responsible Management of Common Areas & Community Safety • Advanced Financial Management for SK Officials • Comprehensive Procurement Systems & Compliance • Strategic Resource Allocation & Sustainability Planning
Pillar 5	Ethical, Inclusive, and Adaptive Governance	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Advanced Gender Sensitivity & Inclusive Governance • Ethical Conduct & Accountability in Public Service • Fostering a Culture of Continuous Professional Development • Strategic Foresight & Adaptive Leadership

Pillars of Sustained Youth Leadership Development

Pillar 1: Foundational Governance & Critical Thinking

This pillar is designed to help Sangguniang Kabataan (SK) officials develop strong analytical and decision-making skills, so they can go from just knowing the basics to using their knowledge effectively in complicated governance situations. It directly addresses core competency, which received the lowest mean rating in the TNA. As cited in the revised Implementing Rules and Regulations (IRR) of Republic

Act 10742 (2023), the state shall establish adequate, effective, responsive, and enabling mechanisms and support systems that empower the youth and ensure their meaningful participation in local governance and nation-building.

Moreover, a study conducted by Madrid et al. (2020) revealed that SK officials in Pangasinan City are knowledgeable in some core areas; however, there were fewer topics and training covered. Hence, a need for continuous reinforcement and advanced application of these foundational skills is crucial because the SK environment is dynamic, with evolving challenges, new policies, and a constant influx of new officials due to electoral cycles and age limits. Given the regular turnover of SK officials, there is a need for fundamental governance skills to be consistently taught to new batches, necessitating a "continuous development" approach within the long-term strategy. This ensures that the core competencies are maintained and deepened across successive SK administrations.

Key Modules/Topics Evolution:

SK Mandate & Legal Framework:

Advanced understanding of Republic Act No. 10742 (SK Reform Law) and its Implementing Rules and Regulations (IRR), including recent amendments, legal accountability, and the implications of SK actions. This ensures officials operate within their legal bounds and leverage their authority effectively. It would also be beneficial to understand the historical background of youth local governance development in the Philippines to render the rationale of SK reforms, and focus on training on administrative processes, budget, and transparency practices required by the law to provide SK officials with techniques to use in governance (Kelsey & Fuhrman, 2020).

Advanced Information Analysis & Data Interpretation:

Training on utilizing diverse data sources, including the mandated youth profiling database, statistical literacy, and identifying underlying trends to inform evidence-based policy and program design and training on the ethical use of data and privacy principles to develop responsible information handling among young

leaders so that they adhere to data protection regulations and enhance confidence in the community (Setiadi, Nurhayati, Ansori, A., Zubaidi, & Amir, 2022)). Additionally, it can be in the form of practical tasks related to data visualization tools in order to achieve data clarity and the ability to communicate intricate findings of data to the stakeholders. This takes the understanding of data to the next level, strategic use of data.

Critical Thinking & Problem-Solving:

Application of advanced frameworks such as root cause analysis, systems thinking, and scenario planning to complex, multi-faceted youth issues, moving beyond immediate solutions to sustainable, systemic interventions through integrated collaborative problem-solving workshops to build consensus and harness diverse perspectives within youth councils and community partners

Effective Decision-Making:

Simulation-based training for high-pressure decision-making, ethical dilemmas, and advanced consensus-building techniques within the SK council and with the Katipunan ng Kabataan (KK), fostering collaborative and accountable governance and making frameworks that incorporate emotional intelligence and stakeholder empathy to improve inclusivity, ethical reasoning, and long-term community buy-in (Kelsey & Fuhrman, 2020).

Pillar 2: Strategic Youth Project Design & Implementation

The targeted areas for this pillar will positively transform the thinking of Sangguniang Kabataan (SK) officials, ensuring that they become effective project developers and innovators. The primary goal is to empower them to successfully transform developing youth problems into long-term, practical, and quantitative projects that meet community expectations. In relation, this goal aligns with the study conducted by Bawit et al. (2024), highlighting social inclusion and equity, active citizenship, and economic empowerment as the top priorities for Sangguniang Kabataan programs, which are critical for ensuring that youth are provided with equal opportunities, civic education, and resources to navigate economic challenges.

Moreover, such capabilities would comprise the previously mentioned crucial features of technical competence and project development, which are the primary objectives of the SK's mandate in launching and developing successful projects. The SK's primary job in accordance with its mandate is to create, plan, and implement projects.

Key Modules/Topics Evolution:

Innovative Solution Generation & Program Design:

Workshops on design thinking, co-creation with youth (Katipunan ng Kabataan – KK), and developing multi-sectoral programs that align with the Comprehensive Barangay Youth Development Plan (CBYDP) and the Philippine Youth Development Plan (PYDP). Augment with methodologies for iterative prototyping and piloting of interventions, emphasizing feedback loops from diverse youth groups to heighten responsiveness and impact (UNOSSC Y4S Program, 2017). Incorporate training on the use of technology and digital tools for program development and virtual collaboration, enabling innovation even in resource-constrained settings.

Adaptive Leadership and Change Management:

Equip youth leaders with skills to navigate complexity, foster resilience, and lead community change initiatives. This involves understanding change dynamics, building stakeholder coalitions, and responding flexibly to emerging challenges. This includes frameworks for assessing organizational and community readiness for change and managing resistance. Add real-world case studies on successful youth-led change projects to inspire practical application (UNOSSC Y4S Program, 2017). Emphasize the role of continuous learning and reflective practice to improve leadership agility and program outcomes

Civic Engagement and Community Mobilization Strategies:

Training youth in grassroots organizing, stakeholder engagement, and participatory decision-making processes. Focus on skills to mobilize local assets, foster inclusive dialogues, digital civic engagement tools, social media advocacy, and leverage networks for broader impact. And sustain community support for youth initiatives.

Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) Integration:

Training on aligning youth programs with the global sustainability agenda to promote multidimensional impact. This includes understanding relevant SDGs, setting measurable goals, tracking progress, and mapping local youth issues to specific SDGs to foster relevance. Also, encourage partnerships with NGOs, government agencies, and the private sector to amplify resources and expertise for SDG achievement.

Evaluation and Reflective Practice in Program Design:

Build capacity for systematic monitoring and evaluation (M&E), including setting indicators, collecting and analyzing data, and using findings for iterative program improvement.

Pillar 3: Collaborative Leadership & Community Mobilization

The aim of this pillar is to create SK officials as capable collaborators and community organizers who could build large-scale partnerships and organize volunteers to participate in youth projects, with the emphasis on the competency of leadership and volunteer mobilization. The external collaboration and the community involvement are the primary determinants of what the Sangguniang Kabataan can accomplish in terms of conducting a wide range of youth development activities. Additionally, Joubert (2024) emphasizes that collaborative leadership provides numerous advantages for organizations. At the executive tier, it promotes unity among leaders, enabling swift and effective business decision-making, establishing and upholding the organization's core values, and strategically tackling challenges as an integrated, cohesive team.

Enhancing these capabilities enables SK to avail of the wider resources and support of the community and make efficient use of the same to transcend the limitations of resources of their own competence and budget, because a single government institution, especially those at the barangay level, where resources are lacking, cannot perform its mandate in isolation. SK has to interact and work with outsiders effectively. Lastly, collaborative leadership and community mobilization fit

under SDG 17, which aims to “Strengthen the means of implementation and revitalize the Global Partnership for Sustainable Development” (United Nations, 2023).

Key Modules/Topics Evolution:

Advanced Stakeholder Mapping & Engagement Strategies:

Techniques for identifying, analyzing, and engaging diverse stakeholders, including local government units (LGUs), civil society organizations (CSOs), the private sector, and international development partners. Stakeholder mapping provides insights for developing successful stakeholder engagement strategies and also highlights a better understanding of the dynamics and interactions of many stakeholders by highlighting their ties, impact, and interests.

Strategic Partnership Building & Management:

Workshops on formalizing inter-agency and cross-sectoral partnerships, developing Memoranda of Understanding (MOUs), establishing joint ventures, and sustaining long-term collaborations, drawing lessons from LGA's comprehensive partnership framework. Also, contained in it is the process of successful partnership building and the key components of an effective strategic partnership that ensure growth and mutual success for all collaborating agencies or organizations.

Effective Volunteer Mobilization & Management:

Best practices in recruiting, training, motivating, and retaining volunteers, recognizing their crucial role in extending SK's reach and amplifying program impact. This includes understanding volunteer motivations, legal frameworks, the establishment of a strategic volunteer management plan, and crafting a narrative that is convincing and clarifies the goals and purpose of a volunteer program.

Advanced Conflict Resolution & Consensus Building:

Training in mediation, negotiation, and fostering consensus within the SK council, with the Katipunan ng Kabataan (KK), and among diverse community groups to ensure smooth project implementation and harmonious community relations. This also includes the discussion on conflict resolution strategies, creating ways that

support peacebuilding, and a discussion about the vital role of youth in peacebuilding.

Pillar 4: Operational Excellence & Fiscal Responsibility

The pillar is centered on equipping SK officials with practical knowledge in the administration and finances of an efficient, responsible, and transparent government, including functional and ordinary skills such as financial management. Responsive governance including putting up a trust in the minds of the population and in giving effective provision of service are fiscal accountability and operational capability is key to the restoration of trust in government (Brillantes & Fernandez, 2021). The training in these matters should be sustained and more frequently done to guide the youth on governing accounting policies and procedures relative to the proper recording and reporting of the funds entrusted to them, since the funds invested in SK need to have a full disclosure of transactions to the population (Commission on Audit, 2021). The popularity of confidence and financial responsibility in terms of funding at the barangay level can be seen in the 10 percent barangay budget that was awarded to SK. A lack of transparency or poor management can significantly undermine trust.

Key Modules/Topics Evolution:

Responsible Management of Common Areas & Community Safety: Advanced training on disaster risk reduction and management (DRRM) tailored for youth, climate change adaptation strategies, and ensuring overall community well-being, integrating gender-responsive approaches as highlighted by funding mechanisms like AGCF.

Advanced Financial Management for SK Officials: In-depth training on budgeting processes, financial reporting, internal controls, and auditing principles specifically for the 10% barangay budget, ensuring strict adherence to regulations, transparency, and accountability. This builds on the BLGF's Training of Trainers on LGU financial tools.

Comprehensive Procurement Systems & Compliance:

Detailed understanding of government procurement laws and regulations (e.g., those from GPPB), ensuring ethical, efficient, and compliant acquisition of goods and services for SK projects. This also gives emphasis to the transparent and accountable procurement processes and the discussion about the standards in terms of quality.

Strategic Resource Allocation & Sustainability Planning:

Training on optimizing resource utilization, exploring alternative revenue streams beyond the annual budget, and developing robust financial sustainability plans for long-term youth programs and initiatives.

Pillar 5: Ethical, Inclusive, and Adaptive Governance

The pillar aims at preparing Sangguniang Kabataan (SK) officials with much-needed skills; encouraging volunteer participation, and spurring project creation. It also equips them with readiness to face the hustle and bustle of government through its development of a good moral compass, a strong sense of inclusivity, and a variable nature. Technical competencies are not the only things needed for effective, sustainable, and trustworthy governance; it has to be based on a strong ethical base, commitment to diversity, and the ability to change and adapt. Those important soft skills, which are often neglected, are essential to promote innovation, build trust in SK activities among the population, and guarantee its sustainability and beneficial contribution in the long run.

The approach of this pillar is also supported by other evidence in the current literature. Research has cited the vital role of gender sensitivity training and inclusive governance in enabling the Sangguniang Kabataan officials to represent and serve different youth groups. As an example, a detailed Gender Sensitivity Training program (2025) explains how gender sensitivity training enhances gender dynamics perception and facilitates equal participation in youth programs and budget-making undertakings. In addition, studies conducted on Sangguniang Kabataan Mandatory Training highlight the importance of incorporating aspects of ethical behavior,

accountability, and adaptive leadership to create a trustworthy governance that is not rigid to emerging issues (Alcantara & Segundo, 2025).

These collectively confirm the Pillar 5 emphasis on building technical competencies with robust ethical backgrounds, inclusiveness, and adaptive competencies to maintain youth-leadership influence. It is remarkable to say that the Training Needs Analysis (TNA) originally revealed that Gender Sensitivity Training was the least rated (in terms of mean values). This brings to the limelight a gap so critical that it goes beyond simple technical knowledge down to the levels of personal beliefs and behaviors necessary to enable inclusive governance.

Key Modules/Topics Evolution:

Advanced Gender Sensitivity & Inclusive Governance:

Deepening understanding of gender dynamics, LGBTQIA+ inclusion, and ensuring all youth programs, policies, and communication are inherently gender-sensitive, free from bias, and promote equitable participation, leveraging insights from gender-responsive funding initiatives. Thus, a Gender-Responsive Budgeting Workshop for SK officials can become a sample activity, in which they learn how to analyze their Annual Barangay Youth Investment Program (ABYIP) to ensure that funds are allocated in a way that benefits all youth, regardless of gender or sexual orientation.

Ethical Conduct & Accountability in Public Service:

Comprehensive training on anti-corruption measures, conflict of interest, the importance of full public disclosure requirements, and upholding the highest standards of integrity and public trust. This includes case studies and ethical dilemma simulations. A scenario-based workshop would fit in this, since SK officials need to have the ability to balance their decision where they know how to resolve conflicts of interest, potential consequences, and come up with an ethical action plan based on existing SK policies and the principles of public trust.

Fostering a Culture of Continuous Professional Development:

Encouraging lifelong learning, self-assessment, mentorship, and peer-to-peer

knowledge sharing among SK officials, recognizing SK service not just as a civic duty but as a legitimate and valuable career pathway within public service.

Strategic Foresight & Adaptive Leadership:

Training on anticipating future challenges (e.g., impacts of climate change, rapid digital transformation, emerging youth issues), developing resilience, and leading adaptively in complex and uncertain environments to ensure the SK remains relevant and effective. A Barangay Resilience Action Planning workshop can be used as a simulation activity. SK officials can conduct a simple "risk assessment" of their barangay and identify which youth groups or communities are most vulnerable to specific climate impacts. With this, they did not only get knowledge, they also got some grasp on what and where they can assess in times of calamity

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

Conclusion

The overall examination of the data acquired gives a clear vision of the demographic profile of the respondents and their self-assessment of the level of competency across various fields. This study was conducted on 223 participants and the distribution in terms of gender was quite even, with 49.8 percent of the sample being female and 50.2 percent male participants, making it a fully balanced sample of the evaluation. The college level of educational law attainment was predominant among the participants, with 70.9 at college level being attended, with an additional 19.7 at college graduate level, which implies a highly intelligent group of the population received the survey. The respondents were also mixed, residing in different cities and municipalities, among which Kapalong, New Corella, Tagum, and Carmen were represented the most, which implies a wide regional reach of the research results.

Findings showed high competency gaps among Davao del Norte SK officials in all areas of core, technical, leadership and functional expertise as well as in the areas of common skills, project development and volunteer mobilisation. The evaluation revealed that SK officials have low proficiency levels, on the average, on

these domains thus signifying the necessity to build capacity in the majority of the respondents. Moreover, these findings firmly support the need for Training Needs Analysis, Sundari and Aksara (2022), emphasizing training needs analysis as a data collection technique used to compare and identify the organization's actual performance level with the expected or planned performance level. Hence, applying this theory can help address the competency gaps faced by the Sangguniang Kabataan (SK) officials.

The fact that these are very low levels of proficiency in essential skills impedes the effectiveness and efficiency of SK officials in the discharge of their duties and scope in youth governance and community developments. The results of the research highlight the necessity of an intensive, specific, and competency-based training that should be used to eliminate these gaps. In addition, the theory of Competency-Based Training (CBT) is parallel to the findings of this study which highlights the importance of aligning the desired training plan with those specific skills that gathered the lowest proficiency levels. This way officials at SK will be better positioned to carry out their functions as well as to foster inclusive and ethical governance and lead the youth in initiatives that will make a significant impact on both the local and national development.

In conclusion, the research was able to determine the key skill barriers and learning requirements of SK officials in Davao del Norte and this formed a substantial empirical basis of developing targeted training and development programs to improve effectiveness of the youth leaders and to empower youth governance in the province.

Recommendation

The current study's results have shown significant gaps in the core, technical, functional, and leadership competencies of Sangguniang Kabataan (SK) officials in Davao del Norte. While quantitative data has successfully highlighted these skill gaps, obtaining deeper contextual insights that contribute to these findings is necessary for the development of meaningful programs. In this regard, the study presents the following recommendations for future research and development.

Future research should consider qualitative methodologies such as in-depth interviews, focus group discussions, and case studies involving SK officials, the local community, and local government partners. Compared to quantitative surveys, qualitative methods allow researchers to explore the realities behind the statistics more profoundly by capturing the lived experiences, problems, and perspectives of SK officials. This type of information provides a powerful background narrative that explains why certain skill deficiencies exist and how officials navigate their mandates within their socio-political contexts. Such understanding is vital for developing training programs that are participatory and responsive to the real needs of youth leaders, so incorporating qualitative research approaches is essential.

Additionally, conducting longitudinal studies to assess the impact of training is vital. Longitudinal research following SK officials before and after training programs should be undertaken to measure competency development, governance processes, and community outcomes over time. Such studies provide evidence of the effectiveness and sustainability of capacity-building activities, thereby facilitating ongoing improvement and accountability in youth leadership development.

Moreover, investigating behavioral, cultural, and attitudinal dimensions is crucial. The study identified low performance in sensitive areas such as gender sensitivity and governance ethics, which often stem from underlying values and beliefs. Future research should explore these behavioral and cultural dimensions by examining personal attitudes, social norms, and organizational cultures influencing SK officials' behaviors concerning emerging inclusive and adaptive leadership. Gaining insight into these intangible but significant aspects will empower policymakers and trainers to design interventions that promote not only knowledge acquisition but also substantial changes in attitudes and behaviors, thus fostering more progressive and less biased youth governance.

Finally, strengthening policy frameworks to support SK development is imperative. The study emphasizes the urgent need to improve policies that not only mandate training but also institutionalize it as part of continuous professional development expected in SK governance. Policy reforms should include consistent

competency assessments, accountability systems, and dedicated funding for SK capacity-building programs. Furthermore, policies must address inclusiveness and gender sensitivity to close existing gaps in these critical areas. Strengthening the policy environment ensures that training interventions become sustainable, coordinated, and adequately resourced, fostering a commitment to systemic improvements rather than temporary fixes.

In conclusion, by implementing these recommendations, future research will deepen the understanding of the challenges faced by SK officials and create practical knowledge to strengthen youth governance. This multi-faceted and context-sensitive research agenda will guide the creation of practical and sustainable training programs and policies that empower SK officials to fulfill their concrete role in nation and community building.

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Appendix A
Notice to Commence

DAVAO DEL NORTE STATE COLLEGE

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president@dnsc.edu.ph
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Institute of Leadership, Entrepreneurship and Good Governance

Notice to Commence for Thesis

Date: January 24, 2025

To: Bautista, Halil G., Superales, Carl Archeer F., Deluvino Joymie E., Vertudazo Brylle S.

Based on the submitted revised research/thesis manuscript, you are hereby recommended to commence the conduct of your study entitled Training Need Analysis of the Sangguniang Kabataan Officials in the Province of Davao del Norte. As such, you are required to secure permission from the concern authorities involved in your study and strictly observe proper protocols in conducting *qualitative/quantitative/mixed method* research design.

Recommending Approval:

GLENNE B. LAGURA, DPA
Thesis Instructor

GLENNE B. LAGURA, DPA
BPA Program Chairperson

Approved by:

FLORIE ANN L. FERMIL, MAEd
Dean

Note: Please attached the accomplished Research Proposal Approval Form

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Love of God and Country

BAGONG PILIPINAS

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Appendix B
Survey Questionnaire

Introduction

Greetings!

We are Halil G. Bautista, Carl Archeer F. Superales, Brylle S. Vertudazo, and Joymie E. Deluvino, 3rd-year Bachelor of Public Administration students of Davao del Norte State College. We are conducting research entitled “**TRAINING NEEDS ANALYSIS OF THE SANGGUNIANG KABATAAN OFFICIALS IN THE PROVINCE OF DAVAO DEL NORTE.**”. The objectives of this study are to assess the current level of skills and competencies of Sangguniang Kabataan (SK) officials in terms of core competencies, technical competencies, leadership competencies, functional competencies, and core skills, and to develop a training design intended for Sangguniang Kabataan officials.

You are chosen as one of the respondents of the study, being elected and appointed as a Sangguniang Kabataan official in your barangay. Please be assured that any information you provide will be treated with utmost confidentiality. Your privacy will be protected throughout the research process, and the information gathered will only be utilized for academic and research purposes.

Consent

I willingly consent to participate in this research. I understand that participation in this research is voluntary and I am free to withdraw my consent to participate at any time in this study.

Name & Signature of Participant

Personal Information

Instruction: Please provide the answers needed in each item by filling out the spaces provided.

Name (Optional): _____

Barangay: _____

Sex: Male Female

Educational Attainment

Elementary

Vocational Graduate

High School

Bachelor's Degree Graduate

College Undergraduate

Graduate Studies

Survey Questionnaire

Instruction: Read each item carefully then respond in a manner that most accurately reflects your perception of the frequency and intensity of your behavior as Sangguniang Kabataan official in your barangay. Referring to the scale below, please indicate the degree of your agreement or disagreement in each statement by checking the number of your choice.

5. Very low proficiency
4. Low proficiency
3. Proficient
2. High proficiency
1. Very high proficiency

PART I. SKILLS AND COMPETENCIES SCALE

Item	Skills and Competencies	Level of Proficiency				
		5 Very low	4 low	3 proficient	2 high	1 Very high
	A. Core Competencies					
1.	The ability to positively and promptly act on new/changing demands in the systems, policies, and the bureaucratic process of the Sangguniang Kabataan.	5	4	3	2	1
2.	The ability to use appropriate language, tone, approaches, materials, and platforms to varying audiences, through spoken and written means.	5	4	3	2	1
3.	The ability to apply understanding of the formal structures, policies, informal norms, cultures within and outside one's workplace, and guidelines around the SK.	5	4	3	2	1

4.	The ability to make efficient or fruitful use of one's time, particularly at serving youth.	5	4	3	2	1
5.	The ability to analyze information, remain calm under pressure, critical thinking, and to have a good sense of decision making	5	4	3	2	1
	B. Technical Competencies	5	4	3	2	1
		Very low	low	proficient	high	Very high
1.	The ability to identify, record, classify, process, share and develop accurate information based on objective study.	5	4	3	2	1
2.	The capacity to identify, define and analyze youth issues, obstacles and opportunities, and generate possible/alternative solutions.	5	4	3	2	1
3.	The ability to possess knowledge of youth development principles and apply them in relevant contexts.	5	4	3	2	1
4.	The capacity to successfully plan, implement, and complete projects within deadlines and quality standards.	5	4	3	2	1
5.	The ability to produce clear, concise, and professional documentation or reports.	5	4	3	2	1
	C. Leadership Competencies	5	4	3	2	1
		Very low	low	proficient	high	Very high
1.	The ability to actively establish and strengthen relationships to support youth initiatives.	5	4	3	2	1
2.	The ability to make timely and well-informed decisions, considering the implications for all stakeholders.	5	4	3	2	1
3.	The ability to bring people together to work towards shared goals for youth development.	5	4	3	2	1
4.	The ability to set objectives and design plans to achieve measurable outcomes.	5	4	3	2	1
5.	The capacity to anticipate future trends and craft strategies to achieve long-term goals.	5	4	3	2	1
	D. Functional Expertise	5	4	3	2	1
		Very low	low	proficient	high	Very high

1.	The capacity to manage resources efficiently and develop an accurate budget to support organizational goals.	5	4	3	2	1
2.	The capacity to design, implement, and evaluate training programs to enhance skills and knowledge.	5	4	3	2	1
3.	The capacity to draft policy papers or position papers in relation to RA 10742 and other youth related policies in accordance with ethical practices.	5	4	3	2	1
4.	The capacity to apply information and abilities in the performance of work activities and responsibilities as applied to functional area.	5	4	3	2	1
5.	The capacity to responsibly manage and organize common areas and user services and to ensure the well-being and safety of the community.	5	4	3	2	1

PART II. SPECIFIC TRAINING AND DEVELOPMENT

Instruction: Please rate the level of Competency in each of the following training and development on a scale from 1 to 5, where:

- 5- Very Low Competency
- 4- Low Competency
- 3- Intermediate Competency
- 2- High Competency
- 1- Very High Competency

Item	A. Common Skills	Level of Competency				
		5 Very low	4 low	3 proficient	2 high	1 Very high
1.	Project Development and Implementation	5	4	3	2	1
2.	Disaster-Risk and Reduction Management (RA 10121)	5	4	3	2	1
3.	Parliamentary Procedure	5	4	3	2	1
4.	Policy Analysis	5	4	3	2	1
5.	Social media-based Government	5	4	3	2	1
6.	Financial Management	5	4	3	2	1
7.	Gender Sensitivity Training	5	4	3	2	1
8.	Research and Extension Training	5	4	3	2	1
9.	Graphic Design	5	4	3	2	1
10.	Procurement Systems	5	4	3	2	1

11.	Knowledge Management	5	4	3	2	1
12.	Human Behavior in Organizations	5	4	3	2	1

Item		Level of Competency				
		5	4	3	2	1
	B. Project Development	Very low	low	proficient	high	Very high
1.	The ability to align Project Sustainable Development Goals with projects as a priority.	5	4	3	2	1
2.	The ability to make use of project planning tools for successful project execution.	5	4	3	2	1
3.	The capacity to understand the importance of drafting compelling project proposals in order to gain funds and support.	5	4	3	2	1
4.	The ability to effectively manage stakeholders and risk for the project's success.	5	4	3	2	1
5.	The ability to manage the cost of the project to stay within the budget.	5	4	3	2	1
6.	The ability to execute projects and efficiently adjust to changes.	5	4	3	2	1
7.	The ability to efficiently use the software and systems to document, finalized and create a comprehensive report that analyzes and summarizes the overall performance of the project.	5	4	3	2	1
	C. Volunteer Mobilization	Very low	low	proficient	high	Very high
1.	The ability to build connections in the civil society for a successful volunteer recruitment.	5	4	3	2	1
2.	The capacity to strategically plan activities to build partnerships with NGOs	5	4	3	2	1
3.	The capacity to effectively manage the voluntary sector to gain successful volunteer initiatives.	5	4	3	2	1
4.	The ability to comply with global standards for enhancing volunteer experiences.	5	4	3	2	1

5.	The capacity to understand the importance of the legal framework of Volunteer Service Management and its effectiveness.	5	4	3	2	1
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Adapted from:

National Pagpakanug (2024, August 7). Capability Building Program on Leadership and Good Governance: A Training for the Sangguniang Kabataan (SK) Officials of Panabo City

National Youth Commission (2021). Guidebook on the Competency Framework for SKs and LYDOs.

Appendix C

Validation Sheets

DAVAO DEL NORTE STATE COLLEGE

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Institute of Leadership, Entrepreneurship and Good Governance

January 30, 2025

Glenn B. Lagura, DPA
Bachelor of Public Administration Faculty
Institute of Leadership and Good Governance

Dear Sir Lagura,

We the group of Halil G. Bautista, Carl Archeer F. Superales, Brylle S. Vertudazo, Joymie E. Deluvino is currently developing the thesis entitled ***“Training Needs Analysis of the Sangguniang Kabataan officials in the Province of Davao Del Norte”*** which will utilize a quantitative instrument designed to analyze and assess the training needs of the SK officials. We believe that through this instrument, we will be able to efficiently gather valuable information necessary for this study.

As part of our development process, we are seeking expert validation of the instrument's content and construct validity. Given your extensive experience and expertise, we humbly request for your assistance in reviewing the instrument and provide feedback.

Attached in this letter is a copy of the instrument and the validation form. We understand that your time is valuable, and we are happy to offer a small amount of honorarium to compensate your efforts. We are confident that your valuable input will significantly contribute to the improvement of our instrument. Thank you for considering our request. We look forward to hearing from you soon.

Respectfully,

Carl Archeer F. Superales
Researcher

Brylle S. Vertudazo
Researcher

Noted:

Romalie F. Galero, MSDeA
Adviser

Halil G. Bautista
Researcher

Joymie E. Deluvino
Researcher

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Institute of Leadership, Entrepreneurship and Good Governance Validation Form (Quantitative)

Title: Training Needs Analysis of the Sangguniang Kabataan Officials in the Province of Davao del Norte

Researcher/s: Halil G. Bautista, Carl Archeer F. Superales, Brylle S. Vertudazo, Joymie E. Deluvino.

Please check the appropriate box indicating your honest rating of the item below. Your response will improve further this interview guide and suggestions are likewise welcome.

Point Equivalent

5-Excellent 4-Very Good 3-Good 2-Fair 1-Needs Improvement

Criteria	Description	Rating				
		5	4	3	2	1
Clarity of items and directions	The vocabulary level, language, structure and conceptual level of the questions suit the level of participants. The directions and the items are written in clear and simple language.	/				
Presentations/Organization of Items	The items are presented and organized in logical manner.	/				
Suitability of Items	The items appropriately represent the substance of the research. The questions are designed to determine the conditions, knowledge, skills and attitude that are supposed to be measured.	/				
Adequateness of Items per category/indicator	The items represent the coverage of the research adequately. The number of questions is representative enough of all questions needed for the research.	/				
Attainment of Purpose	The instrument as a whole fulfils the objective for which it was constructed.		/			
Objectivity	The items in the questionnaire are formulated prudently and are free of prejudicial conceptions.	/				

Overall Remarks:

Glenne B. Lagura, DPA

February 20, 2025

Signature over Printed Name of Evaluator

Date of Evaluation

VISION
A premier Higher Institution in Agri-Fisheries and Socio-cultural Development in the ASEAN Region.

MISSION
DNSC strives to produce competent human resource, generate, and utilize knowledge and technology, uphold good governance and quality management system for sustainable resources and resilient communities.

CORE VALUES
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Stewardship
Love of God and Country

DAVAO DEL NORTE STATE COLLEGE

New Visayas, Panabo City, Davao del Norte, 8105

president@dnsc.edu.ph ✉
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@davnorstacollege f

Institute of Leadership, Entrepreneurship and Good Governance

February 21, 2025

Marcel Marie T. Dagohoy, MPA
Bachelor of Public Administration Faculty
Institute of Leadership and Good Governance

Dear Ma'am Dagohoy,

The group of Halil G. Bautista, Carl Archeer F. Superales, Brylle S. Vertudazo, Joymie E. Deluvino is currently developing the thesis entitled "*Training Needs Analysis of the Sangguniang Kabataan officials in the Province of Davao Del Norte*" which will utilize a quantitative instrument designed to analyze and assess the training needs of the SK officials. We believe that through this instrument, we will be able to efficiently gather valuable information necessary for this study.

As part of our development process, we are seeking expert validation of the instrument's content and construct validity. Given your extensive experience and expertise, we humbly request for your assistance in reviewing the instrument and provide feedback.

Attached in this letter is a copy of the instrument and the validation form. We understand that your time is valuable, and we are happy to offer a small amount of honorarium to compensate your efforts. We are confident that your valuable input will significantly contribute to the improvement of our instrument. Thank you for considering our request. We look forward to hearing from you soon.

Respectfully,

Carl Archeer F. Superales
Researcher

Brylle S. Vertudazo
Researcher

Halil G. Bautista
Researcher

Joymie E. Deluvino
Researcher

Noted:

Romalie F. Gallego, MSDeA
Adviser

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@davnorstatecollege f

Institute of Leadership, Entrepreneurship and Good Governance Validation Form (Quantitative)

Title: Training Needs Analysis of the Sangguniang Kabataan Officials in the Province of Davao del Norte

Researcher/s: Halil G. Bautista, Carl Archeer F. Superales, Brylle S. Vertudazo, Joymie E. Deluvino.

Deluvino.

Please check the appropriate box indicating your honest rating of the item below. Your response will improve further this interview guide and suggestions are likewise welcome.

Point Equivalent

5-Excellent 4-Very Good 3-Good 2-Fair 1-Needs Improvement

Criteria	Description	Rating				
		5	4	3	2	1
Clarity of items and directions	The vocabulary level, language, structure and conceptual level of the questions suit the level of participants. The directions and the items are written in clear and simple language.	✓				
Presentations/Organization of Items	The items are presented and organized in logical manner.	✓				
Suitability of Items	The items appropriately represent the substance of the research. The questions are designed to determine the conditions, knowledge, skills and attitude that are supposed to be measured.	✓				
Adequateness of Items per category/indicator	The items represent the coverage of the research adequately. The number of questions is representative enough of all questions needed for the research.	✓				
Attainment of Purpose	The instrument as a whole fulfils the objective for which it was constructed.	✓				
Objectivity	The items in the questionnaire are formulated prudently and are free of prejudicial conceptions.	✓				

Overall Remarks:

Marcel Marie T. Dagohoy, MPA

Signature over Printed Name of Evaluator

February 21, 2025

Date of Evaluation

VISION
Premier Higher Institution
in Fisheries and Socio-
Economic Development in
the Davao Region.

MISSION
DNSC strives to produce competent human
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Love of God and Country

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New Visayas, Panabo City, Davao del Norte, 8105

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@davnorstatecollege

Institute of Leadership, Entrepreneurship and Good Governance

February 21, 2025

Joanaros P. Fahit, RSW, MSSW
Bachelor of Science in Social Work Faculty
Institute of Leadership and Good Governance

Dear Ma'am Fahit,

We, group of Halil G. Bautista, Carl Archeer F. Superales, Brylle S. Vertudazo, Joymie E. Deluvino under the Bachelor of Public Administration is currently developing the thesis entitled "**Training Needs Analysis of the Sangguniang Kabataan officials in the Province of Davao Del Norte**" which will utilize a quantitative instrument designed to analyze and assess the training needs of the SK officials. We believe that through this instrument, we will be able to efficiently gather valuable information necessary for this study.

As part of our development process, we are seeking expert validation of the instrument's content and construct validity. Given your extensive experience and expertise, we humbly request for your assistance in reviewing the instrument and provide feedback.

Attached in this letter is a copy of the instrument and the validation form. We understand that your time is valuable, and we are happy to offer a small amount of honorarium to compensate your efforts. We are confident that your valuable input will significantly contribute to the improvement of our instrument. Thank you for considering our request. We look forward to hearing from you soon.

Respectfully,

Carl Archeer F. Superales
Researcher

Brylle S. Vertudazo
Researcher

Noted:

Romalie F. Galleto, MSDeA
Adviser

Halil G. Bautista
Researcher

Joymie E. Deluvino
Researcher

VISION
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in Agriculture, Fisheries and Socio-
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New Visayas, Panabo City, Davao del Norte, 8105

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dnc.edu.ph
@davnorstacollege

Institute of Leadership, Entrepreneurship and Good Governance
Validation Form (Quantitative)

Title: Training Needs Analysis of the Sangguniang Kabataan Officials in the Province of Davao del Norte

Researcher/s: Halil G. Bautista, Carl Archeer F. Superales, Brylle S. Vertudazo, Joymie E. Deluvino.

Please check the appropriate box indicating your honest rating of the item below. Your response will improve further this interview guide and suggestions are likewise welcome.

Point Equivalent

5-Excellent 4-Very Good 3-Good 2-Fair 1-Needs Improvement

Criteria	Description	Rating				
		5	4	3	2	1
Clarity of items and directions	The vocabulary level, language, structure and conceptual level of the questions suit the level of participants. The directions and the items are written in clear and simple language.	✓				
Presentations/Organization of Items	The items are presented and organized in logical manner.		✓			
Suitability of Items	The items appropriately represent the substance of the research. The questions are designed to determine the conditions, knowledge, skills and attitude that are supposed to be measured.	✓				
Adequateness of Items per category/indicator	The items represent the coverage of the research adequately. The number of questions is representative enough of all questions needed for the research.	✓				
Attainment of Purpose	The instrument as a whole fulfils the objective for which it was constructed.	✓				
Objectivity	The items in the questionnaire are formulated prudently and are free of prejudicial conceptions.	✓				

Overall Remarks:

Please check comments written in the instrument.

Joanaros P. Fatit, RSW, MSSW

February 21, 2025

Signature over Printed Name of Evaluator

Date of Evaluation

VISION
Premier Higher Institution
in Fisheries and Socio-
economic Development in
DAN Region.

MISSION
DNSC strives to produce competent human
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technology, uphold good governance and
quality management system for sustainable
resources and resilient communities.

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Appendix D

Reliability Statistics

Core Competencies (5 items)

Cronbach's Alpha: 0.978 Very High Reliability

Item	Scale Mean if Item Deleted	Scale Variance if Item Deleted	Corrected Item-Total Correlation	Cronbach's Alpha if Item Deleted
CC1	8.8529	19.584	0.905	0.978
CC2	8.8235	18.392	0.933	0.973
CC3	8.8824	17.804	0.939	0.973
CC4	8.9412	18.057	0.949	0.971
CC5	8.9706	18.939	0.964	0.969

Technical Competencies (5 items)

Cronbach's Alpha: 0.884 High Reliability

Item	Scale Mean if Item Deleted	Scale Variance if Item Deleted	Corrected Item-Total Correlation	Cronbach's Alpha if Item Deleted
TC1	10.1471	13.402	0.699	0.865
TC2	10.2353	12.428	0.742	0.855
TC3	10.1471	13.220	0.759	0.852
TC4	10.2647	13.049	0.672	0.871
TC5	10.1471	12.614	0.742	0.855

Leadership Competencies (5 items)

Cronbach's Alpha: 0.873 High Reliability

Item	Scale Mean if Item Deleted	Scale Variance if Item Deleted	Corrected Item-Total Correlation	Cronbach's Alpha if Item Deleted
LC1	9.7353	10.746	0.763	0.832
LC2	9.6176	10.001	0.734	0.839
LC3	9.6176	9.637	0.747	0.837
LC4	9.5882	11.280	0.750	0.838
LC5	9.6765	12.347	0.548	0.880

Functional Expertise 5 items)

Cronbach's Alpha: 0.864 High Reliability

Item	Scale Mean if Item Deleted	Scale Variance if Item Deleted	Corrected Item-Total Correlation	Cronbach's Alpha if Item Deleted
FE1	9.7941	10.956	0.774	0.811
FE2	9.9706	11.242	0.774	0.812
FE3	9.7647	11.822	0.628	0.849
FE4	9.6471	11.205	0.766	0.814
FE5	9.8824	13.198	0.487	0.880

Common Skills (12 items)

Cronbach's Alpha: 0.981 Very High Reliability

Item	Scale Mean if Item Deleted	Scale Variance if Item Deleted	Corrected Item-Total Correlation	Cronbach's Alpha if Item Deleted
CS1	24.7353	117.594	0.787	0.982
CS2	24.5588	115.769	0.877	0.980
CS3	24.5294	115.893	0.925	0.979
CS4	24.5294	113.105	0.945	0.978
CS5	24.5588	115.466	0.892	0.979
CS6	24.5588	115.102	0.856	0.980
CS7	24.6765	110.710	0.921	0.979
CS8	24.4706	115.166	0.891	0.979
CS9	24.6471	116.357	0.872	0.980
CS10	24.4412	114.072	0.913	0.979
CS11	24.6471	113.326	0.910	0.979
CS12	24.7059	112.638	0.935	0.978

Project Development (7 items)

Cronbach's Alpha: 0.938 Very High Reliability

Item	Scale Mean if Item Deleted	Scale Variance if Item Deleted	Corrected Item-Total Correlation	Cronbach's Alpha if Item Deleted
PD1	15.6765	27.498	0.827	0.925
PD2	15.5000	26.864	0.805	0.928
PD3	15.6765	28.953	0.758	0.931
PD4	15.4412	28.012	0.827	0.925
PD5	15.5882	28.250	0.838	0.924
PD6	15.7353	28.625	0.766	0.931
PD7	15.4412	29.406	0.768	0.931

Volunteer Mobilization 5 items)

Cronbach's Alpha: 0.936 Very High Reliability

Item	Scale Mean if Item Deleted	Scale Variance if Item Deleted	Corrected Item-Total Correlation	Cronbach's Alpha if Item Deleted
VM1	10.4706	14.802	0.926	0.902
VM2	10.3824	16.486	0.801	0.926
VM3	10.3235	15.741	0.777	0.932
VM4	10.2941	16.335	0.803	0.926
VM5	10.2941	16.032	0.846	0.918

Appendix E
Turnitin AI Report

Halil Bautista

Manuscript of Bautista et. al (4).docx

- BPA Research
- BPA Research
- Davao del Norte State College

Document Details

Submission ID

trn:oid::11980:105628158

Submission Date

Jul 24, 2025, 3:00 PM GMT+8

Download Date

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File Name

Manuscript of Bautista et. al (4).docx

File Size

19.5 MB

92 Pages

16,006 Words

98,912 Characters

*% detected as AI

AI detection includes the possibility of false positives. Although some text in this submission is likely AI generated, scores below the 20% threshold are not surfaced because they have a higher likelihood of false positives.

Caution: Review required.

It is essential to understand the limitations of AI detection before making decisions about a student's work. We encourage you to learn more about Turnitin's AI detection capabilities before using the tool.

Disclaimer

Our AI writing assessment is designed to help educators identify text that might be prepared by a generative AI tool. Our AI writing assessment may not always be accurate (it may misidentify writing that is likely AI generated as AI generated and AI paraphrased or likely AI generated and AI paraphrased writing as only AI generated) so it should not be used as the sole basis for adverse actions against a student. It takes further scrutiny and human judgment in conjunction with an organization's application of its specific academic policies to determine whether any academic misconduct has occurred.

Frequently Asked Questions

How should I interpret Turnitin's AI writing percentage and false positives?

The percentage shown in the AI writing report is the amount of qualifying text within the submission that Turnitin's AI writing detection model determines was either likely AI-generated text from a large-language model or likely AI-generated text that was likely revised using an AI-paraphrase tool or word spinner.

False positives (incorrectly flagging human-written text as AI-generated) are a possibility in AI models.

AI detection scores under 20%, which we do not surface in new reports, have a higher likelihood of false positives. To reduce the likelihood of misinterpretation, no score or highlights are attributed and are indicated with an asterisk in the report (*%).

The AI writing percentage should not be the sole basis to determine whether misconduct has occurred. The reviewer/instructor should use the percentage as a means to start a formative conversation with their student and/or use it to examine the submitted assignment in accordance with their school's policies.

What does 'qualifying text' mean?

Our model only processes qualifying text in the form of long-form writing. Long-form writing means individual sentences contained in paragraphs that make up a longer piece of written work, such as an essay, a dissertation, or an article, etc. Qualifying text that has been determined to be likely AI-generated will be highlighted in cyan in the submission, and likely AI-generated and then likely AI-paraphrased will be highlighted purple.

Non-qualifying text, such as bullet points, annotated bibliographies, etc., will not be processed and can create disparity between the submission highlights and the percentage shown.

Appendix F
Turnitin Similarity Report

Halil Bautista

Manuscript of Bautista et. al (4).docx

 Davao del Norte State College

Document Details

Submission ID

trn:oid::11980:105628158

Submission Date

Jul 24, 2025, 3:00 PM GMT+8

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File Name

Manuscript of Bautista et. al (4).docx

File Size

19.5 MB

92 Pages

16,006 Words

98,912 Characters

14% Overall Similarity

The combined total of all matches, including overlapping sources, for each database.

Filtered from the Report

- Submitted works

Match Groups

- 142** Not Cited or Quoted 11%
Matches with neither in-text citation nor quotation marks
- 8** Missing Quotations 0%
Matches that are still very similar to source material
- 20** Missing Citation 3%
Matches that have quotation marks, but no in-text citation
- 0** Cited and Quoted 0%
Matches with in-text citation present, but no quotation marks

Top Sources

- 13% Internet sources
- 6% Publications
- 0% Submitted works (Student Papers)

Integrity Flags

0 Integrity Flags for Review

No suspicious text manipulations found.

Our system's algorithms look deeply at a document for any inconsistencies that would set it apart from a normal submission. If we notice something strange, we flag it for you to review.

A Flag is not necessarily an indicator of a problem. However, we'd recommend you focus your attention there for further review.

Appendix G
Certificate of Grammarian

Grammarians Certificate

This is to certify that the undersigned has thoroughly reviewed and proofread the research paper titled:

“Learning Needs Assessment of the Sangguniang Kabataan Officials in the Province of Davao del Norte”

The report has been meticulously examined to ensure that it aligns with the structural rules governing the composition of sentences, phrases, and words in the English language. It adheres to academic standards of grammar, clarity, and coherence.

All grammatical corrections and necessary recommendations have been made and duly incorporated into the final version of the research study.

Issued this 30th day of October 2025.

Signed:

ROLANDO B. ACOSTA, LPT

Grammarians/English Editor

MAED-English – 2nd Year (Ongoing)

Appendix H

Letter to Conduct

DAVAO DEL NORTE STATE COLLEGE

New Visayas, Panabo City, Davao del Norte, 8105

president@dnsc.edu.ph
dnsc.edu.ph
@davnorstalecollege

Institute of Leadership, Entrepreneurship and Good Governance

March 25, 2025

JONATHAN J. LEYBAG
DIRECTOR, DILG DAVAO DEL NORTE

Dear Sir/Maam,

We are Halil G. Bautista, Carl Archeer F. Superales, Brylle S. Vertudazo, and Joymie E. Deluvino, 3rd-year Bachelor of Public Administration students of Davao del Norte State College. We are conducting research entitled **"TRAINING NEEDS ANALYSIS OF THE SANGGUNIAN KABATAAN OFFICIALS IN THE PROVINCE OF DAVAO DEL NORTE."** The objectives of this study are to assess the current level of skills and competencies of Sangguniang Kabataan (SK) officials in terms of core competencies, technical competencies, leadership competencies, functional competencies, and core skills and develop a training design intended for Sangguniang Kabataan officials.

Consequently, we formally request permission from your office to conduct the said research study with the Sangguniang Kabataan Officials as our respondents within the Province of Davao del Norte. We believe that with your approval and support, this study will make a substantial contribution to the improvement of Sangguniang Kabataan Officials' performance in serving the youth.

Thank you for considering our request.

Respectfully,

CARL ARCHEER F. SUPERALES
Researcher

BRYLLE S. VERTUDAZO
Researcher

Reviewed:

ROMALIO F. GALLETTO, MSDEA
Adviser

Noted by:

GLENNE B. LAGURA, DPA
Program chairperson

HALIL G. BAUTISTA
Researcher

JOYMIE E. DELUVINO
Researcher

SPO - Discaya
Received by:

PAUL JOHN P. ESCOBIER
PS II SPO Discaya
Date: _____

VISION MISSION CORE VALUES

CURRICULUM VITAE

PERSONAL DETAILS

- HALIL G. BAUTISTA

CONTACT DETAILS

- +63-951-3882-511
- bautista.halil@dnsc.edu.ph

PERSONAL DATA

Birth Date: April 11, 2003
 Age: 22
 Height : 5'5
 Weight: 55 kg
 Religion: Islam
 Civil Status: Single
 Nationality: Filipino
 Address: Purok Ramihan, Datu Abdul Dadia, Panabo City, Davao del Norte
 Father's Name: Rene M. Bautista
 Mother's Name: Edna G. Bautista

EDUCATION BACKGROUND

Elementary : Rizal Elementary School 2009-2015
Secondary : Panabo City National High School 2015-2019
 Panabo City Senior High School 2020-2021
Tertiary : Davao del Norte State College (Main Campus) 2022-Present
 Bachelor of Public Administration

TRAININGS AND SEMINARS

- Project MAKI-ALAM: A Symposium on the Role of Institutions, Media, and Citizen Participation in Government Development (May 2025)
- Tinubdan: A Symposium on the Foundations of Governance and Development (May 2025)
- PAGPAKANUG 2025: Capability Building Program on Leadership and Good Governance (April 2025)
- PAGESANDONG 2025: Strengthening Political Awareness for Responsible and Informed Choices (April 2025)
- PAGPAKANUG 2024: Capability Building Program on Leadership and Good Governance (August 2024)
- PAGESANDONG 2024: A Seminar on Authentic Leadership and Parliamentary Rules and Procedure (April 2024)
- Step to Serve: Volunteerism as a form of Active Citizenship Webinar (2022)
- How to Ace: Academic Writing and Public Speaking Webinar (2022 and 2023)

EXTRA-CURRICULAR AND ORGANIZATIONAL AFFILIATIONS

- DNSC - Coalition of Future Public Administrators Vice-President (2024-Present)
- DNSC - ILEGG Students Organization Board Member (2023-2024)
- PCNHS - Supreme Student Government Representative (2020-2021)

PERSONAL DETAILS

- CARL ARCHEER F. SUPERALES

CONTACT DETAILS

- +63-991-5164-778
- superales.carlarcheer@dpsc.edu.ph

PERSONAL DATA

Birth Date: October 24, 2003
 Age: 21
 Height : 5'8
 Weight: 80 kg
 Religion: Roman Catholic
 Civil Status: Single
 Nationality: Filipino
 Address: Purok 10-A ,Alejal Carmen, Davao del Norte
 Father's Name: Cristino R. Superales
 Mother's Name: Anabel F. Superales

EDUCATION BACKGROUND

Elementary : Alejal Elementary School 2010-2016
Secondary : Carmen National High School 2016-2020
 Carmen National High School 2020-2022
Tertiary : Davao del Norte State College (Main Campus) 2022-Present
 Bachelor of Public Administration

TRAININGS AND SEMINARS

- PAGPAKANUG 2025: Capability Building Program on Leadership and Good Governance (August 2024)
- PAGPAKANUG 2024: Capability Building Program on Leadership and Good Governance (August 2024)
- How To Ace: Academic Writing and Public Speaking 2022
- Issues and Trend: Teenage Pregnancy (2022)
- Step To Serve: Volunteerism as a Form of Active Citizenship (2022)
- Anti drug campaign seminar participant (2019)
- HIV awareness symposiums participant (2019)

EXTRA-CURRICULAR AND ORGANIZATIONAL AFFILIATIONS

- DNSC - FSC Congressperson (2025-2026)
- SSC Senator (2024-2025)
- DNSC - SSC ILEGG Representative (2023-2024)

PERSONAL DETAILS

- BRYLLE S. VERTUDAZO

CONTACT DETAILS

- +63-915-3266-938
- vertudazo.brylle@dncs.edu.ph

PERSONAL DATA

Birth Date: September 7, 2003
 Age: 21
 Height : 5'6
 Weight: 65 kg
 Religion: Roman Catholic
 Civil Status: Single
 Nationality: Filipino
 Address: Purok 5, Tubod, Carmen, Davao del Norte
 Father's Name: Ricky B. Vertudazo
 Mother's Name: Nardely S. Vertudazo

EDUCATION BACKGROUND

Elementary : Don Manuel A. Javellana Memorial Elementary School 2010-2016
Secondary : Tubod National High School 2016-2020
 University of Mindanao Panabo College 2020-2022
Tertiary : Davao del Norte State College (Main Campus) 2022-Present
 Bachelor of Public Administration

TRAININGS AND SEMINARS

- Project MAKI-ALAM: A Symposium on the Role of Institutions, Media, and Citizen Participation in Government Development (May 2025)
- PAGPAKANUG 2025: Capability Building Program on Leadership and Good Governance (April 2025)
- How To Ace: Academic Writing and Public Speaking (April 2022)
- Emergency Service Training Course (April 2018)
- Moral Recovery Program and Drug Symposium (September 2017)
- One-Day Anti-Terrorism Awareness (September 2017)
- Step to Serve: Volunteerism as a form of Active Citizenship Webinar (2022)

EXTRA-CURRICULAR AND ORGANIZATIONAL AFFILIATIONS

- Boy Scout of the Philippines Eagle Scout (2016-Present)
- Supreme Pupil Government Vice-President (2015-2016)
- Barkada Kontra Droga (2017-2018)

PERSONAL DETAILS

- JOYMIE E. DELUVINO

CONTACT DETAILS

- +63-9317274625
- Deluvino.joymie@dnsc.edu.ph

PERSONAL DATA

Birth Date: March 10,2002
 Age: 23
 Height : 5'4
 Weight: 61kg
 Religion: Evangelical Christian
 Civil Status: Single
 Nationality: Filipino
 Address: Purok Nangka, Gredu, Panabo, Davao del Norte
 Father's Name: Melchor C. Deluvino
 Mother's Name: Arfel E. Deluvino

EDUCATION BACKGROUND

Elementary : Central Elementary School 2008-2013

Secondary : Panabo City National High School 2014-2018
University of Mindanao Panabo 2018-2020

Tertiary : Davao del Norte State College (Main Campus) 2021-Present
 Bachelor of Public Administration

TRAININGS AND SEMINARS

Tinubdan: A Symposium on the Foundations of Governance and Development (May 2025)
 PAGPAKANUG 2025: Capability Building Program on Leadership and Good Governance (April 2025)
 PAGESANDONG 2023: A Seminar on Volunteerism and Parliamentary Rules and Procedure (April 2023)
 Seminar on Fundamentals and Importance of Research Interventions in Public Administration (December 2023)
 Project YOUTHUNITED: Peer Educators Training (2023)
 Step to Serve: Volunteerism as a form of Active Citizenship Webinar (2022)
 How to Ace: Academic Writing and Public Speaking Webinar (2022)
 Child Friendly Space Disaster Response and Community Development Training (2019)

EXTRA-CURRICULAR AND ORGANIZATIONAL AFFILIATION

Nazarene Youth International Local President (2017-Present)
 Nazarene Youth International Zone President (2022-2024)
 Nazarene Youth International District Representative (2022-Present)

